
**D4.14 Report from 4th
cogwheel workshop**

WP4 Joint integrative projects

Responsible Partner: SVA

Contributing partners: NVI

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Report from Cogwheel Workshop 4 One Health EJP / InfAct

Introduction

In Work Package 4 (WP4) of the One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP), EU initiatives that require strategic interaction with OHEJP are identified in collaboration with WP2 and WP5, to avoid redundancy and to further leverage the alignment at EU level. One of the instruments, so called cogwheel workshops, are being organised by WP4 to allow key actors and relevant partners within the OHEJP, typically Project leaders or WP leaders within Joint Research Projects (JRPs) or Joint Integrative Projects (JIPs), to identify synergies, joint priorities and opportunities for collaboration within the OHEJP or with other EU initiatives. Before contacting the relevant EU initiative/project, it is important to identify and collect (common) JRP and JIP needs and to define if the initiative complies with these needs. Furthermore, it is important to see if the initiative can complement or assist the OHEJP, for instance with database/repositories, protocols, advice, practical collaboration (sequencing, bioinformatics) and so on.

Eight CWs will be organised during the OHEJP. The reports from cogwheel workshops will be part of the input to the Strategic Research Agenda (SRA) of WP2, as well as the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of WP7.

The target for the fourth cogwheel workshop was the InfAct (Information for Action) project. InfAct (<https://www.inf-act.eu/>) is a 36 months project funded by the European Commission that started in March 2018. A total of 40 partners and 28 countries are involved. The project is coordinated by SCIENSANO. The goal of InfAct is to strengthen national and EU health information systems. This is done by;

- Establishing a sustainable research infrastructure to support population health and health system performance assessment.
- Strengthening European health information and knowledge bases, as well as health information research capacities to reduce health information inequalities.
- Supporting health information interoperability and innovative health information tools and data sources.

The cogwheel will ensure that OHEJP development is complementary and that potential synergies are identified.

Practicalities

- Information about the upcoming cogwheel workshop was sent to all OHEJP Project leaders and deputies and members of the Scientific Steering Board (SSB) on 19 December 2019. Information about InfAct was included.
- Three OHEJP projects identified InfAct as a relevant project to learn more about, to avoid duplication and/or to have potential for synergies with the OHEJP. Unfortunately, the

representative from one OHEJP project was unable to attend the CW due to unforeseen circumstances. Thus, two OHEJP projects were represented, namely ORION and MATRIX.

- The cogwheel workshop was held as an online meeting using Adobe Connect at 22 January 2020. The agenda is included in the annex.

Attendance list

Project	Representatives (institution)
ORION	Matthias Filter (BfR) Fernanda Dórea (also MATRIX, SVA)
MATRIX	Katrin Kuhn (SSI) Viviane Hénaux (ANSES)
OHEJP WP5	Ludovico Sepe (BfR)
OHEJP WP2	Maria Ugarte-Ruiz (VISAVET-UCM)
OHEJP WP4	Marie Nykvist (SVA) Solveig Sølverød Mo (NVI)

Output

All OHEJP projects interested in participating in the cogwheel workshop had the opportunity to do so. The relevant key elements in InfAct, as identified by each OHEJP project, are listed below. The proposed action points from each project are listed in a separate summary table below.

Meeting summary, per project

Key elements in InfAct relevant for each EJP project:

EJP Project	ORION
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarification on “harmonization approach” pursued in InfAct → there is no overlap between ORION and InfAct • Clarification on development status of other resources that could have been of interest for ORION → solutions from InfAct seem to be less mature than those developed by ORION, partly the envisaged solutions have yet not been conceptually designed.

EJP Project	MATRIX
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We didn’t identify any important points of overlap or congruence. • Their work is very much focused on health data at a patient level, while MATRIX focuses on surveillance.

Summary table Action points

Project	Action points	Who, when
ORION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inform InfAct about Virtual Research Environment as a potential resource for DIPoH (The Distributed Infrastructure for Population Health, InfAct WP7) • Inform InfAct about the OHEJP ASM 2020 as potential place to meet and exchange knowledge face to face (InfAct coordination) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Matthias Filter, beginning of February

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Inform InfAct about OH-CRAC (One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist, ORION WP1) as this could be of interest for InfAct WP8 Task 8.3• Inform InfAct about the Health Surveillance Ontology created by ORION WP3 as potential resource for InfAct WP9	
MATRIX	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• None identified	

Other comments:

- InfAct seems to have a tight interaction with national policy and decision makers. Their strategy of interaction is interesting for WP5 – Science to policy translation
- InfAct’s Assembly of Members seems to correlate to our POC. Interesting to hear that they focus more on national partners, rather than international ones like ECDC. They seem to have good and strong contacts with the national partners. Maybe this is something we can learn from, rather than struggling to reach ECDC etc.
- A good project to learn about. Not worried that there are major overlaps, as their interest is quite separate from that of the OHEJP. There seem to be no need to take any specific contacts with InfAct.

Concluding remarks

Representatives from the OHEJP were content with the cogwheel workshop. In general, no major overlaps between InfAct and the OHEJP projects represented were identified. The participants were happy with the online format of the meeting. It was suggested that the future cogwheel workshops could be recorded and made accessible for OHEJP members after. A PDF including all presentations held by InfAct was distributed to all OHEJP participants.

Presentations given at the meeting

See Annex.